

DIRECTIONS D6.2:

Report on time domain validation of DC protection for Belgian energy hub

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This report presents the validation of the protection system design for the *Belgian Energy Hub*, as developed in Task 6.1: *Choice and specification of Belgian energy hub DC protection strategy*, and Task 6.2: *Design of DC protection and configuration for Belgian energy hub*. This validation constitutes the final stage of the general protection system design methodology, which was developed in Work Package 3 of the DIRECTIONS project. It is situated within Task 6.3: *Time-domain validation of case study specific functional performance*.

The outcomes of the protection system design, as presented in Deliverable 6.1, are considered, in this report, in a thorough *system-level performance evaluation* study through extensive electromagnetic transient time-domain simulations. They are evaluated for three metrics that represent the protection system operation, HVDC grid impact and AC grid fault impact, namely: the maximum current in HVDC circuit breakers, the converter fault-ride-through capabilities, and the AC-side active power loss of infeed. These performance tests are conducted for a wide range of input conditions and operational scenarios, in addition to the critical scenarios identified for the design, to validate previous findings for the selection of these critical cases and to show the suitability of the protection system design for all conditions.

The methodology and results of the validation are presented in detail in this report. First, a clear overview of the considered system and design outcomes is provided, followed by a detailed description of the input values that make up the different scenarios tested in the simulations. An automated simulation and testing framework, which was developed for the execution of the validation study, is also presented. Finally, the simulation results are analyzed in detail using the performance metrics, to arrive at a clear conclusion on the validation of the design and the selection of critical cases.

The results of the validation show that the design outcomes from Deliverable 6.1 remain valid when considering the additional parameters and scenarios that are not included in the original design. It is also shown that the considered design margin of 10 % decreases, in the worst case, to 4 % in the validation, due to the variation of the fault time.

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